

**FOOD INSECURITY AND FOOD PROGRAMS : OPINION SURVEY IN TAMIL
NADU****R. Isha Bhavanti¹****K. Kirubakaran²****ABSTRACT**

Food security exists when everyone has accessibility, availability and affordability to a good amount of healthy safe nutritious food on a stable basis. Food insecurity proves to be the alter ego of food security by showing the negative consequences when food is unavailable and inaccessible on both qualitative and quantitative basis. The research aims to study food insecurity in relation to the food programs that are available to take people away from food insecurity. A questionnaire-based survey was taken with a convenient sampling and information collected from 233 respondents. The results show that food insecurity and availability of food programs are greatly related to the variables like locality, occupation and income of people. There are many food programs working on to curb food insecurity and hunger among people. The research gives suggestions on how to end food insecurity which includes effective food programs and relation with human security, with zero-hunger miles away from the current way of handling food insecurity.

Keywords : food insecurity, availability, accessibility, affordability, hunger, health.

INTRODUCTION

Food insecurity exists whenever food is limited or uncertain. It refers to the disruption of food intake or eating habits because of lack of money and other resources. The measurement of food insecurity at the individual or household level involves the evaluation of the quantitative, qualitative, psychological and social or normative criteria that concentrate on the experience of food insecurity, improved by their unpredictability and persistence. The concept of food security started at the end of the World Wars and the formation of world-wide intergovernmental organisations like the League of Nations and the United Nations. The causal agents for food insecurity mainly include poverty, non-availability, poor environmental conditions, natural calamities, overpopulation and climate change effects on food productivity. Potential consequences of food insecurity include hunger, malnutrition and negative effects on health and quality of life, either directly or indirectly. The relationships between food insecurity, its risk factors and the solutions to food insecurity are in need of much research. Measurement of food insecurity is being done by various programs and organisations. In India, there are Public Distribution Systems (PDS) for providing food for households but it is not properly implemented in all the parts of the nation. Proper food programs for alleviation of food

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insecurity specifically in different nations aren't many. Governmental food programs fail to get rid of hunger in their respective areas. A few fail to reach their objective while others are not well-received and utilised by people. Awareness on these food programs in each one's area is much needed. Food insecurity needs to be looked at based on many aspects mainly availability, accessibility, affordability, stability, qualitative and quantitative basis. To alleviate hunger from the food availability level, the Green Revolution was brought into the world helping in increasing food productivity. There are programs which help in increasing food productivity but the farmers are not benefited properly. All these need to be looked at while working on food security for all. Though the affordability aspect is largely looked at around the world, the accessibility and the quality of food is to be looked into to secure the health of people. Food security and human security are considered to be interlinked to each other. Human security aims at ensuring the survival, livelihood and dignity of people according to current and emerging threats which is not limited to those living in absolute poverty or conflict. The relationship between food security and human security is based on the idea of taking food security as a part of the fundamental human rights of every person. By approaching food security from the perspective of human security will help in building resilience on food security and nutrition. Nevertheless, food security as of now depends on good and promising food programs which can help in the alleviation of the existing hunger and malnutrition and work for zero hunger. There is also a need for awareness and knowledge about food security and quality life. Working for the right to food can be done by working on the grass root level regarding food security in the current scenario.

OBJECTIVES

Objectives of the study are

- To analyse the food programs formed to combat food insecurity in different parts of the India.
- To examine the food programs that are available in Tamil Nadu and how they are received by the people.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Bhattacharya et al. (2004) have examined the connection between the health status, poverty and food insecurity of members of households of various ages. They have used data from National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey III and found that food insecurity and poverty is predictive in adults while food insecurity is not predictive among school children. They concluded that caution must be taken while assuming connections between food insecurity and nutritional outcomes, especially in children.

Kumar et al. (2020) have examined the prevalence of food insecurity at household level and its associated factors in rural level and its associated factors in rural Puducherry. They have done a community based cross-sectional study among the rural Puducherry and questionnaire based questions were asked to adult females. They have also used secondary data of the Household Food Insecurity Access Scale. They found out that out of 299 households assessed,

31.7% were food insecure, i.e., one in three families experienced food insecurity and is more among households with children. They concluded that nutrition based disorders need to be addressed and prevented in the community and there is a need for effective PDS and Food Benefit Schemes.

Singh et al. (2021) have discussed food insecurity during COVID-19 pandemic among people from the disadvantaged community and low income families in Province 2 of Nepal. They have used primary data using semi structured interviews among purposely selected participants from both rural and urban areas in 8 districts of Province 2, Nepal. They suggested that relief support plans and policies should be focussed on implementation of immediate sustainable food insecurity and strategies to prevent hunger, malnutrition and mental health problems are needed among the most vulnerable groups of the community.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The current study is based on empirical research. Convenient sampling method is used (Non-probability sampling). The sample size is 233. Data is collected through online sources. Information has been collected demographic variables such as age, Gender, Educational Qualification, Occupation and Locality and Affordability, accessibility, quantity, quality, sufficiency and anxiety in relation to food security

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Figure 1 :

Legend : Pie chart showing how many people are benefitted from food programs.

Figure 2 :

Legend : Pie chart showing how many respondents volunteer in food programs.

Figure 3 :

Legend : Figure 3 shows the age and the occupation of the respondents in a form of a clustered bar graph.

Figure 4 :

Legend : Figure 4 represents the income of the respondents based on their locality.

Figure 5 :

Legend : Figure 5 represents the accessibility and the availability of food for the respondents based on their locality.

Figure 6 :

Legend : Figure 6 represents the dependence on food programs by the sample respondents based on their income per month.

RESULTS

In Figure 1, we can see how many respondents are benefiting from food programs in their areas. 52.1 % of the respondents are either not benefited from the food programs or don't need to depend on any food programs.

In Figure 2, we can see how many respondents are volunteering in food programs in their areas. Only 9 % of the respondents help and volunteer in food programs.

In Figure 3, we can see about the occupation of the respondents based on their age. Those who are less than 20 years old are unemployed. The other age groups are either unemployed or employed.

In Figure 4, we can confer about the income of the respondents based on where they reside. The respondents living in the rural areas earn less than the respondents who live in suburban and urban areas. People in the urban areas earn more than the respondents who live in rural and suburban areas.

In Figure 5, we can confer about the accessibility and availability of food based on their locality. The respondents living in the rural areas have given mixed answers regarding the accessibility and availability of food. This can be due to the outreach of food programs like the Public

Distribution Systems available there. The respondents living in the urban areas have access and availability of food almost all the time. The respondents of the suburban areas, who are less in number in the sample frame, also have good access to food.

In Figure 6, we can confer about the dependence on the food programs by the respondents based on their income per month. We can see that people earning above Rs. 30,000 don't depend on the food programs.

In Table 1, we can understand that there is a significant relationship between income per month and borrowing of money by the respondents to fulfil their daily requirements of food as the p value is 0.000 and is less than 0.50. Hence, we can confer that people earning more money rarely or never borrow to fulfil their daily requirements of food.

In Table 2, we can understand there is a statistically significant relationship between the independent variable, locality and the dependent variable, availability of money to buy enough food by the respondents and their households. We can see that the t - value is more than 2, here, it is 6.883. By Figure 4, we know that people in rural areas earn less than people living in urban and suburban areas. So, we can confer that money needed to buy enough food is dependent on the income of the people. Hence, there is an impact on the money available for buying enough food based on their locality.

DISCUSSION

Food programs are received by people in a variable manner (Figure 1 and Figure 2). Though 41.9 % of the respondents are dependent on the food programs, many don't volunteer in food programs (93 %). From this, we can infer that food programs are received by people well but taking part in such programs is very less. From the analysis we have done, we can see that a number of people aged below 20 are unemployed (Figure 3). From Figure 4, we can see that the people in urban areas are earning more than the others. This shows that urban areas provide people with jobs with more salary. This indirectly implies that people in urban areas are able to access and avail food. Food insecurity has affected the people in the rural areas more than the people in urban areas. It is found that food accessibility and availability is in relation to the area people reside in (Figure 5). Here we can see that Figure 4 and Figure 5 are related. When people who live in an area which gives good job opportunities and an adequate salary, they are able to access and avail food. In Figure 6, we come to know about the dependence on food programs based on the respondents' income per month. We see that people who earn nil have also stated that they are not dependent on food programs. This is because these respondents are aged below 20 years and are not working and most probably are students who are dependent on their parents or guardians. We saw earlier that areas which give good jobs and salary make food accessible and available. But in this graph, it doesn't look so because the majority or almost all the respondents who have stated nil dependence on food programs are students in urban areas. In

Table 1, we confer the relationship between income per month and borrowing of money. This we can understand by looking at the string of events as before. When people earn more, they are able to support themselves. Hence, they don't find the need to borrow money. In Table 2, we understand that there is a significant relationship between locality and availability of money to buy food. As we saw earlier, since urban areas give more opportunities and are more developed than the other localities, people in urban areas are able to buy enough food on their own without borrowing money. Hence, we can understand that food insecurity and availing food programs greatly depend on the independent variables of locality, occupation and income of people.

LIMITATION

The major limitation of this study is the sample frame. The samples were collected through online platforms like sending mail, sending links via WhatsApp. This is the limitation of the study. The real field experience is missed out due to the COVID-19 pandemic. The restrictive area of sample size is yet another drawback of the research. Collection of data via online platforms is limiting the researcher to collect data from the field. Since the data is collected on an online platform wherein the respondent is not known, the original opinion of the respondent is not found and this research could only come to an approximate conclusion of what the respondent is feeling to convey. Also, since the study has used convenient sampling, we have been unable to get responses from the people who are affected by the research.

SUGGESTIONS

Food insecurity needs to be addressed in all dimensions. We need to improve availability, accessibility, affordability and stability based on both qualitative and quantitative basis. There is a need to improve the technology in agriculture in order to produce good quality yield of crops. There are many significant innovations done in agriculture both in farming and agricultural science which need to be implemented across the world to achieve zero-hunger globally by improving crop production and management. We need climate smart agriculture along with major schemes to combat climate change while fighting food insecurity. Going vegan is also considered as a way to reduce food insecurity. Food needs to be accessible to everyone. This is where many food programs come into action. Food needs to be distributed to each and every person living across the world. The existing food programs need to be supported and micro food programs at regional levels is a need of the hour. As we see from the survey, not many involve themselves in food programs. There are people who help the hungry people on the streets while some involve themselves in religious organisations in providing food for people. There are also people who work with NGOs like Akshaya Patra foundation-ISKCON, Pasumai Padai, Alif Boyz, etc. Food needs to be available at a reasonable price for people. By this aspect, we need effective governmental programs for making food accessible, affordable and available to all. There are governmental programs in Tamil Nadu like the Universal Public Distribution Systems and Amma Unavagam giving affordable and free food for the people. But still, it needs to be improved much more as there are cases of corruption and misuse of money

and other problems faced by these food programs. Most importantly, food security needs to be measured across the areas in order to get a clear idea as to how to implement programs to curb food insecurity and achieve zero-hunger. The easiest yet not looked into is stopping food wastage. There is also a need to ensure food security in other ways. The broader way to stop food insecurity is to make the right to food as a human right. In this way, food will not only be considered as a necessity, but also an integral part of the right to life which cannot be denied to anyone.

CONCLUSION

Food insecurity is a social problem lesser known by people. It happens silently in families across the world. As we have seen here, various methods are exercised to measure and fight food insecurity. However, they are either under-developed or unrecognised by many. Hence, there is a need to improve the food programs so as to make them available and accessible to all. In the study we have seen how food insecurity is dealt with by many countries and how it is in Tamil Nadu. There is a need to make effective policies and programs in uplifting people from hunger and malnutrition which subsequently affects the health and the performance of the people.

Also, we need to understand that though poverty is a major factor leading to food insecurity, there are many other factors that lead to food insecurity. When food is in shortage, even when one is rich, he may not be able to avail food. Improvement in food programs and development in agriculture and growth of sustainable development is very important to curb food insecurity, hunger and malnutrition. There is a need for broadening the concept of food security to the right to food as a part of human rights to achieve the sustainable goals for the development of the society at large.

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